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Clinical paper

Comorbidity and survival in the pre-hospital and in-hospital phase after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest

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Abstract

Introduction: Cumulative disease burden may be associated with survival chances after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA). The relative contributions of cumulative disease burden on survival rates at the pre-hospital and in-hospital phases of post-resuscitation care are unknown.

Methods: The association between cumulative comorbidity burden as measured by the Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI) and pre-hospital and in-hospital survival rates was studied using data (2010–2014) from a prospective OHCA registry in the Netherlands. The association between CCI and survival rate (overall survival [OHCA-hospital discharge], pre-hospital survival [OHCA-hospital admission] and in-hospital survival [hospital admission-hospital discharge]) was assessed using logistic regression analyses. The relative contributions of CCI on pre-hospital and in-hospital survival rates were determined using the Nagelkerke test.

Results: We included 2510 OHCA patients aged ≥ 18 y. CCI was significantly associated with overall survival rate (OR 0.71; 95%CI 0.61–0.83; $P < 0.01$). CCI was not associated with pre-hospital survival rate (OR 0.96; 95%CI 0.76–1.23; $P = 0.92$) whereas high CCI was significantly associated with low in-hospital survival rate (OR 0.41; 95%CI 0.27–0.62; $P = 0.01$). The relative contributions of CCI on pre-hospital and in-hospital survival were 1.1% and 8.1%, respectively.

Conclusion: Pre-existing high comorbidity burden plays a modest role in reducing survival rate after OHCA, and only in the in-hospital phase. The present study offers data that may guide clinicians in discussing resuscitation options during advance care planning with patients with high comorbidity burden. This may be helpful in creating a patients' informed choice.

Keywords: ESCAPE-NET, Comorbidity, Charlson Comorbidity Index, Out-of-hospital cardiac arrest, Survival, Pre-hospital, In-hospital

Introduction

The number of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest (OHCA) patients with a high comorbidity burden is on the rise, while comorbidity burden may impact survival chances after OHCA.^{1–3} Previous investigations of the association between pre-existing comorbidity burden and OHCA survival rates were limited to analysis of overall survival rates (from

OHCA to hospital discharge), and did not distinguish survival rates in the pre-hospital phase (from start OHCA to hospital admission) and the in-hospital phase (from hospital admission to hospital discharge).^{1,2,4,5}

Establishing whether differences in these phases exist is important because it offers patients the opportunity to plan for future care including 'do-not-attempt-resuscitation' (DNAR) orders, according to their preferences and based on an informed choice. Particularly, it is

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valuable to know and understand the relative contributions of cumulative comorbidity burden on survival chances at the pre-hospital and in-hospital phases to be able to appropriately estimate the importance of comorbidity burden. Knowing this, will ultimately improve the patients' informed choice when discussing resuscitation preferences during advance care planning.

This study aimed to identify the (relative) contributions of cumulative comorbidity burden on survival chances at the pre-hospital and in-hospital phases after OHCA.

Methods

Setting

The Amsterdam Resuscitation Study (ARREST) is an ongoing, prospective registry of OHCA in the North-Holland province of the Netherlands. The ARREST study group cooperates with all emergency medical services (EMS) in this study region. The study region covers 2404 km² and has a population of 2.4 million people. Details of the design of the data collection in the ARREST study are described elsewhere.⁶ The present study covered the study period January 1, 2010–December 31, 2014.

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants who survived the OHCA.⁷ The Medical Ethics Review Board of the Academic Medical Center, Amsterdam, approved the study, including the use of data from patients who did not survive the OHCA.

Study population, design and data collection

All patients aged ≥ 18 years in whom EMS personnel attempted resuscitation during OHCA within the study period were included. We excluded from analysis patients with a clear non-cardiac cause according to the Utstein recommendations, a termination of the EMS resuscitation attempt because of DNAR certificate, an incomplete medical history, and those who survived but did not consent to their data being used.

After each resuscitation attempt, EMS personnel routinely sent the continuous ECG from their manual defibrillators to the ARREST study centre. If an automated external defibrillator (AED) was used, ARREST study personnel visited the AED site shortly after OHCA to collect the AED ECG recording. The ECGs were stored and analysed with dedicated software (Code Stat Reviewer 10.1, Physio Control, Redmond WA, USA). The initial rhythm was recorded by manual defibrillator or AED (whichever was first). All resuscitation data were collected according to the Utstein recommendations.⁸ We included the following resuscitation characteristics as covariates: location of OHCA, time from EMS call to defibrillator connection (EMS response time), initial rhythm, and presence/absence of witness, bystander cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), and AED deployment.

All patients who survived to hospital admission were surveyed by retrieving their hospital charts. Data on neurologic outcome at hospital discharge was retrieved from these charts and categorized using the Cerebral Performance Category score: (1) good cerebral performance; (2) moderate cerebral disability; (3) severe cerebral disability; (4) coma or vegetative state; (5) death. A score of 1 or 2 was classified as survival with neurologic favourable outcome. Survival was verified by contacting the hospital of admission and confirmed in the civic registry. Medical history of the patients was obtained from the general practitioner (GP) who, in the Netherlands, has a complete overview of

all diagnoses made by medical specialists. This information was used to calculate the Charlson Comorbidity Index (CCI).⁹ The CCI takes the presence of comorbidities into account weighted on the basis of their association with mortality. Three CCI-categories were identified to obtain patient groups of comparable size: no disease burden (CCI-score 0), moderate disease burden (CCI-score 1 or 2), and high disease burden (CCI-score ≥ 3).⁹

Outcomes

The initial rhythm was categorized as shockable (ventricular tachycardia, ventricular fibrillation) or non-shockable (asystole, pulseless electrical activity). We assessed overall, pre-hospital, and in-hospital survival rates, along with proportions of survival with neurologic favourable outcome. Overall survival was defined as survival from OHCA to alive discharge from hospital. Pre-hospital survival was defined as patients who were admitted alive to any hospital ward at the hospital after OHCA. In-hospital survival was defined as survival from hospital admission to hospital discharge (this only included patients who were hospitalized with ROSC).

Age was used as a continuous variable, but was also categorized into 2 groups (< 70 years or ≥ 70 years).

Statistical analyses

Differences in comorbidity burden between survivors and non-survivors in the group with a known medical history were assessed using chi-square statistics, Student t-test or Mann–Whitney U test, where appropriate. Multivariable logistic regression analyses were performed to test the association between CCI category and a) overall survival b) pre-hospital survival and c) in-hospital survival. Similar analyses were performed when selected for patients with a shockable initial rhythm.

The interaction for CCI-category with sex and age (< 70 years or ≥ 70 years) was calculated and stratified accordingly. In addition, we estimated the relative contributions of comorbidity burden, resuscitation characteristics and demographics to a) pre-hospital survival and b) in-hospital survival. To estimate the relative contribution, we studied the increase in explained variance while adding resuscitation characteristics, demographics and comorbidity burden to the model. Explained variance was determined using the Nagelkerke test.

Analyses were performed in complete cases only (without missing values on any covariate). As a sensitivity analysis, to impute missing covariates of interest, multiple imputations were used with fully conditional specification (Markov Chain Monte Carlo) with 50 iterations and predictive mean matching for scale variables. Five different imputation sets were created. Once imputed we estimated the logistic regression with the imputed data set (in Supplementary Material).

All statistical tests were two-tailed, with $P < 0.05$ considered statistically significant, and performed in SPSS (version 24.0 for Mac). To control for the number of false positives, logistic regression analyses were repeated by reducing the significance level from $P \leq 0.05$ to $P \leq 0.01$.

Results

Demographic and resuscitation characteristics

A total of 2510 patients were included for analysis (eFig. 1). A missing case analysis (eTable 1) revealed no differences between missing

and complete cases in age, sex, proportion of shockable initial rhythm or survival rate. Demographic and resuscitation characteristics of the included patients are shown according to CCI category in Table 1. From the total number of patients, 1227 patients (48.9%) had no disease burden; 744 patients (29.6%) had a moderate disease burden and 539 patients (21.5%) had a high disease burden.

Mean age increased with rising CCI-category (63.3y to 74.6y; $P < 0.01$), while the proportions of men, OHCA at public location, shockable initial rhythm and bystander CPR decreased (Table 1). The proportion of witnessed status, AED use and EMS response time did not differ between the CCI-categories (Table 1). Proportions of pre-existing individual comorbidities (as part of the CCI) of patients in the pre-hospital phase and in the in-hospital phase were described in Table 2.

Similar results were observed in the imputed dataset (eTable 2). The fractions of missing information for primary outcomes were: overall survival 0.1%; pre-hospital survival 0.3%; in-hospital survival 0.0%.

Survival chances

Overall survival

In total, 581 patients (23.1%) survived from OHCA to hospital discharge (no disease burden: $n=357$ [survival rate: 29.1%], moderate disease burden: $n=167$ [survival rate: 22.4%], high disease burden: $n=57$ [survival rate: 10.6%]). Higher comorbidity burden was associated with lower overall survival rate even after adjustment for age, sex, and resuscitation characteristics (OR 0.71; 95%CI 0.61–0.83; $P < 0.01$) and when selected for patients with a shockable initial rhythm (OR 0.80; 95%CI 0.67–0.96; $P=0.02$). Among patients discharged from hospital alive, there was no difference in neurologic favourable outcome between the different CCI-categories ($P=0.45$).

Pre-hospital survival

In the pre-hospital phase, no association was observed between comorbidity burden and survival rate (OR 0.96; 95%CI 0.76–1.23; P for trend = 0.92, Fig. 1A, eTable 3). Likewise, no association was observed when we limited our analysis to patients with a shockable initial rhythm (OR 0.87; 95%CI 0.60–1.27; P for trend = 0.72, eTable 4).

In-hospital survival

In the in-hospital phase, we found an association between high comorbidity burden and lower survival rate (OR 0.41; 95%CI 0.27–0.62, P for trend < 0.01 , Fig. 1B, eTable 5), even when the significance level was reduced from $P < 0.05$ to $P \leq 0.01$. A similar association between high-comorbidity burden and survival was observed when we limited our analysis to patients with a shockable initial rhythm (OR 0.49; 95%CI 0.30–0.80); P for trend = 0.01, eTable 6).

In the multiple imputed datasets, results were comparable to the complete case analysis (eTables 7&8).

Relative contribution of comorbidity burden to OHCA survival

In the pre-hospital phase, resuscitation characteristics alone explained 38.2% ($R^2=0.382$) of the variance in survival rate. Adding demographics to this model resulted in an increase in explained variance to 38.9% ($R^2=0.389$). Finally, after adding comorbidity burden to this model, the explained variance slightly increased to 39.0% ($R^2=0.390$). Likewise, when comorbidity burden was added to the model while resuscitation characteristics and demographics were left out, the explained variance slightly increased for pre-hospital survival (1.1%) ($R^2=0.011$).

In the in-hospital phase, resuscitation characteristics alone explained 31.8% ($R^2=0.318$) of the variance in survival rate. Adding demographics to the model resulted in an increase in explained variance to 39.4% ($R^2=0.394$). Adding comorbidity burden to this model, the explained variance increased to 40.0% ($R^2=0.400$). When comorbidity burden was added to the model while resuscitation characteristics and demographics were left out, an increase of 8.1% ($R^2=0.081$) in explained variance was observed.

Stratification by sex and age

Men were more likely to be diagnosed with a previous myocardial infarction (22.7% vs. women 13.1%; $P < 0.01$) but less likely to be diagnosed with congestive heart failure (17.5% vs. 23.1%; $P < 0.01$), peripheral vascular disease (12.6% vs. 14.8%; $P=0.04$), any malignancy (13.5% vs. 16.6%; $P=0.04$), dementia (2.0 vs. 5.1;

Table 1 – Baseline characteristics CCI.

	Total n=2510	CCI score			P-value
		CCI score 0 n=1227	CCI score 1–2 n=744	CCI score ≥ 3 n=539	
Age in years, mean \pm SD	67.8 \pm 13.8	63.3 \pm 13.7	70.1 \pm 12.4	74.6 \pm 12.0	<0.01
Male sex	1787 (71.2)	922 (75.1)	522 (70.2)	343 (63.6)	<0.01
Male: Age in years, mean \pm SD	66.8 \pm 13.3	62.8 \pm 12.8	69.4 \pm 12.3	73.6 \pm 12.1	<0.01
Female: Age in years, mean \pm SD	70.1 \pm 14.7	64.9 \pm 16.1	71.6 \pm 12.6	76.5 \pm 11.6	<0.01
<i>Resuscitation characteristics</i>					
Witnessed by bystander	1805 (71.9)	887 (72.3)	546 (73.4)	372 (69.0)	0.09
Public location	697 (27.8)	413 (33.7)	201 (27.0)	83 (15.4)	<0.01
Shockable initial rhythm	1229 (49.0)	686 (55.9)	349 (46.9)	194 (36.0)	<0.01
Bystander CPR provided	2000 (79.7)	999 (81.4)	596 (80.1)	405 (75.1)	0.01
AED connected	1433 (57.1)	713 (58.1)	413 (55.5)	307 (57.0)	0.38
Response time in min, median (IQR)	8.4 (6.4–10.6)	8.2 (6.3–10.4)	8.1 (6.4–10.6)	8.7 (6.7–11.0)	0.83

Results are presented as n (%) unless indicated otherwise. AED, automated external defibrillator; CPR, cardiopulmonary resuscitation; IQR, interquartile range.

Table 2 – Pre-hospital and in-hospital survival: individual comorbidities.

	Survivors	Non-survivors
Pre-hospital phase survival		
Previous myocardial infarction (n = 501)	237 (47.3)	264 (52.7)
Congestive heart failure (n = 480)	173 (36.0)	307 (64.0)
Peripheral vascular disease (n = 200)	81 (40.5)	119 (59.5)
Cerebrovascular disease (n = 333)	112 (33.6)	221 (66.4)
Chronic pulmonary disorder (n = 464)	164 (35.0)	300 (65.0)
Diabetes without chronic complications (n = 469)	165 (35.2)	304 (64.8)
Diabetes with chronic complications (n = 92)	38 (41.3)	54 (85.7)
Renal disease (n = 311)	105 (33.8)	206 (66.2)
Mild liver disease (n = 79)	30 (38.0)	49 (62.0)
Peptic ulcer disease (n = 69)	27 (39.1)	42 (60.9)
Any malignancy (n = 361)	132 (36.6)	229 (63.4)
Rheumatologic/connective tissue disease (n = 100)	39 (39.0)	61 (61.0)
In-hospital phase survival		
Previous myocardial infarction (n = 237)	130 (54.9)	107 (45.1)
Congestive heart failure (n = 173)	67 (38.7)	106 (61.3)
Peripheral vascular disease (n = 81)	32 (39.5)	49 (60.5)
Cerebrovascular disease (n = 112)	43 (38.4)	69 (61.6)
Chronic pulmonary disorder (n = 164)	80 (48.8)	84 (51.2)
Diabetes without chronic complications (n = 165)	73 (44.2)	92 (55.8)
Diabetes with chronic complications (n = 38)	17 (44.7)	21 (55.3)
Renal disease (n = 105)	32 (30.5)	73 (69.5)
Mild liver disease (n = 30)	15 (50.0)	15 (50.0)
Any malignancy (n = 132)	56 (42.4)	76 (57.6)
Rheumatologic/connective tissue disease (n = 39)	19 (48.7)	20 (51.3)

*Results are shown as n (row %).

**The following comorbidities were left out of the Table because n was <10: hemiplegia or paraplegia, moderate or severe liver disease, metastatic solid tumor, dementia and HIV or AIDS.

Fig. 1 – Association between comorbidity burden and survival.

Panel A: **Association between comorbidity burden and pre-hospital survival (OHCA to hospital admission).**

ORs are adjusted for sex, age and resuscitation factors (location, response time, and presence of witness or bystander CPR).

Panel B: **Association between comorbidity burden and in-hospital survival (hospital admission to hospital discharge, limited to patients who survived to hospital admission).**

ORs are adjusted for sex, age and resuscitation factors (location, response time, and presence of witness or bystander CPR).

Abbreviations: CCI, Charlson Comorbidity Index; CPR, Cardiopulmonary resuscitation; OR, Odds ratio.

$P < 0.01$) and rheumatologic and connective tissue disease (3.2% vs. 5.8%; $P < 0.01$) (eTable 9).

Interaction terms for sex were pre-hospital phase: $CCI * Sex = 0.06$; in-hospital phase: $CCI * Sex = 0.01$. No significant trend was observed between comorbidity burden and pre-hospital survival rate in either men (P for trend = 0.41; Fig. 2.1.A) or women (P for trend = 0.72; Fig. 2.2.A). In contrast, lower in-hospital survival rates were associated with high disease burden in men (OR 0.34; 95%CI 0.21–0.55; P for trend <0.01; Fig. 2.1.B). In women, a similar trend

was observed but this was not statistically significant (OR 0.68; 95% CI 0.31–1.50; P for trend = 0.33; Fig. 2.2.B).

The interaction terms for age were pre-hospital phase: $CCI * Age = <0.01$; in-hospital phase: $CCI * Age = <0.01$. In the pre-hospital phase, no significant trend was observed between comorbidity burden and pre-hospital survival in either aged <70 years (P for trend = 0.31; Fig. 3.1.A) or aged ≥70 years (P for trend = 0.22; Fig. 3.2.A). In the in-hospital phase, high disease burden was associated with lower in-hospital survival in the group aged <70 years (OR 0.35 95%CI 0.20–0.64; Fig. 3.1.B) but P for

Fig. 2 – Association between comorbidity burden and survival for males and females.

Panel 1.A: **Association between comorbidity burden and pre-hospital survival (OHCA to hospital admission) for men.**

Panel 1.B: **Association between comorbidity burden and in-hospital survival (hospital admission to hospital discharge, limited to patients who survived to hospital admission) for men.**

Panel 2.A: **Association between comorbidity burden and pre-hospital survival (OHCA to hospital admission) for women.**

Panel 2.B: **Association between comorbidity burden and in-hospital survival (hospital admission to hospital discharge, limited to patients who survived to hospital admission) for women.**

ORs are adjusted for age and resuscitation factors (location, response time, and presence of witness or bystander CPR).

Abbreviations: CCI, Charlson Comorbidity Index; CPR, Cardiopulmonary resuscitation; OR, Odds ratio.

Fig. 3 – Association between comorbidity burden and survival for patients aged <70 and patients aged ≥70.

Panel 1.A: **Association between comorbidity burden and pre-hospital survival (OHCA to hospital admission), patients aged <70.**

Panel 1.B: **Association between comorbidity burden and in-hospital survival (hospital admission to hospital discharge, limited to patients who survived to hospital admission), patients aged <70.**

Panel 2.A: **Association between comorbidity burden and pre-hospital survival (OHCA to hospital admission), patients aged ≥70.**

Panel 2.B: **Association between comorbidity burden and in-hospital survival (hospital admission to hospital discharge, limited to patients who survived to hospital admission), patients aged ≥70.**

ORs are adjusted for sex and resuscitation factors (location, response time, and presence of witness or bystander CPR).

Abbreviations: CCI, Charlson Comorbidity Index; CPR, Cardiopulmonary resuscitation; OR, Odds ratio.

trend was not significant (0.10). Also, lower in-hospital survival rates were associated with high disease burden in the group aged ≥ 70 years (OR 0.36, 95%CI 0.19–0.65; *P* for trend < 0.01 ; Fig. 3.2.B).

Discussion

Main findings

We found that higher comorbidity burden was associated with lower overall survival rate. This association stems from the in-hospital phase: comorbidity burden was not associated with pre-hospital survival rate, but high comorbidity burden was associated with lower in-hospital survival rate. A similar association between high comorbidity burden and lower in-hospital survival was observed in patients with a shockable initial rhythm. However, we found that the relative contribution of comorbidity burden to pre-hospital survival was only 1.1%, and 8.1% for in-hospital survival. Resuscitation characteristics remain the most important factors for in-hospital survival.

Discussion of main findings

Previous studies on the association between pre-existing comorbidity burden and overall survival rate showed inconsistent results, varying between an association between higher burden and lower survival rate^{1,2,5} to no significant association.¹⁰ In line with most previous studies, we found that high pre-existing comorbidity burden was associated with lower overall survival rate. A study that found no association, focused on an older aged study population.¹⁰

As observed in previous research, knowledge of advance resuscitation care planning is low in OHCA patients.¹² Our study aimed at broadening the knowledge base that is needed to make such informed decisions regarding advance resuscitation care planning. We provide the novel insight that patients with high comorbidity burden have a comparable survival rate during the pre-hospital phase after OHCA as patients without comorbidity burden. Therefore, our study supports the notion that survival differences in the pre-hospital phase are predominantly influenced by resuscitation factors such as early bystander CPR or time to connection of defibrillator, and not by comorbidity burden.¹¹ However, after hospital admission, patients with high comorbidity burden have significantly lower survival rates. Thus, pre-existing comorbidity burden plays a role in OHCA survival, although this applies solely to the in-hospital phase and not to the pre-hospital phase.

Similar results were found in a sensitivity analysis that was limited to patients with a shockable initial rhythm, one of the most important predictors for survival after OHCA.¹³

Although we found an association between high cumulative comorbidity burden and low in-hospital survival, it should be taken into account that pre-hospital resuscitation characteristics and demographics remain the most important predictors for in-hospital survival (the relative contribution of resuscitation characteristics and demographics to in-hospital survival is 39.4%, while cumulative comorbidity burden alone accounts for 8.1%). At the same time, the relative contribution of cumulative comorbidity burden to in-hospital survival is higher (8.1%) when compared to pre-hospital survival (1.1%), though still modest.

Our findings may guide clinicians in rightfully estimating the relative importance of comorbidity burden to post-resuscitation prognostication. International recommendations emphasize the need for protocol-led prognostication after the first 72 h,¹⁴ but protocols may differ across countries. In the Netherlands, post-resuscitation prognostication is

indicated in patients with prolonged coma after resuscitation. Such prognostication takes place after approximately 3 days. In those with a very poor prognosis the clinician can refrain from further treatment. We had expected that the presence of a cumulative comorbidity burden would play a significant role in the post-resuscitation prognostication. Our findings suggest that this is not so.

Moreover, our findings may offer the opportunity for patients to make better informed advance care planning decisions. For instance, knowing that cumulative comorbidity burden is not associated with pre-hospital survival, patients may elect not to have a DNAR order for the pre-hospital phase after OHCA, because alive admission to the hospital after OHCA may offer their loved ones the opportunity to say farewell to the OHCA patient; only after this, in-hospital treatment may be terminated upon their request or per their previously expressed advance care plan. On the other hand, since patients with high comorbidity burden are more likely to (eventually) die in-hospital, some patients may desire to die at home¹⁵ instead of being brought to the hospital, and thus opt for a DNAR order.

Finally, high disease burden was associated with lower in-hospital survival rate in men. A similar trend was found in women, but this trend was not statistically significant. Our previous research suggested that sex differences in OHCA survival rate may partly be explained by biological differences.¹⁶ Accordingly, we found sex differences in type of pre-existing diseases in the present study, e.g., higher prevalence of previous myocardial infarction and peripheral vascular disease among men. Future research is needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms that might explain the observed association between high comorbidity burden and low in-hospital survival rate.

Strengths and limitations

A strength of the present study is the comprehensiveness of the collected data sets, including data from EMS-dispatch centre, paramedics, hospital and GP thereby providing a complete picture of the circumstances of the OHCA's.

Some important limitations need to be considered; first, comorbidity burden could be underestimated in patients that did not survive to hospital admission, because the patients' comorbidity, used to calculate the CCI score, was gathered using a questionnaire completed by the GP, followed by information obtained from hospital records; from patients declared dead in the field, information from the hospital could not be retrieved. Second, we used the CCI to measure the comorbidity burden. However, the CCI could misrepresent the comorbidity burden that is relevant for survival after OHCA, as it has been validated to predict the one-year mortality of patients who have been hospitalized for diseases such as cancer and liver diseases, while it has not been validated in an out-of-hospital population or in patients with cardiac disease. Still, in order to be able to compare results with previous investigations, we decided to use the CCI.

Conclusion

Pre-existing high comorbidity burden, measured using CCI score, is associated with lower survival rate after OHCA, but only during the in-hospital phase, and explains a modest proportion of survival rate. These findings may guide clinicians in appropriately estimating the relative importance of comorbidity burden when having to perform post-resuscitation prognostication for OHCA patients. It may also offer patients with high-comorbidity burden the opportunity to make better-informed advance care planning decisions.

Conflict of interest

None declared.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resuscitation.2020.05.035>.

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